

MOBILE COMMUNICATION STUDIES: EMERGING THEMES AND CONCERNS

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ABSTRACT

Mobile phone is already regarded as the fastest diffused medium ever. As a corollary of its novelty and social impact, a new interdisciplinary field called mobile communication studies has been formed. The field has emerged with its own multidimensional themes and intellectual concerns with growing number of enthusiast scholars working across regions to contribute in the knowledge production. The field has become a ground of producing new ideas and researches with regard to various issues surrounding mobile communication and its social implications both from micro and macro directions. However, little work has been done for its evaluation. Against this backdrop, the present paper is an attempt to offer an evaluative overview of this new field of academic inquiry by offering a synthesis of various emerging research themes and concerns.

Keywords: *Issues, mobile phone, mobile communication studies, research themes, social implications*

Present century is a digital century. And if one medium which is the driving force of our increasingly becoming digital life, that is definitely the mobile phone. In its initial phases of development, the mobile phone was large and bulky. It was harder to carry, impractical to use and has little public availability. Consequently, its social impact was scant. However, with continuous technological developments and innovative breakthroughs such as the arrival of cell technology and its increasingly miniaturization with the use of transistors and integrated circuits, it became much more portable and usable (For the history of mobile phone see Ling and Donner, 2009). Later, the introduction of systems and services like GSM, SMS, MMS, mobile internet services such as WAP and ultimately the entry of WWW made it a truly utilitarian device. The recent diffusion of cutting edge Smartphone with enormous computing availability has initiated the dawn of the mobile age. As per a global level data, in

2005, there were a total 2, 205 million worldwide mobile subscribers, which by 2020 reached an astonishing 8, 152 million numbers in which developing countries has more mobile users as compared to the developed world (ITU, 2020). Today, the mobile phone has become a lifeline of millions of people across the world who use it for more mundane to more specialized works. No wonder, it has become a pervasive social item.

The massive surge in the mobile's success, and its unprecedented social implications have attracted a group of social scientists, who, very recently, came under the interdisciplinary title of *Mobile Communication Studies*. These scholars are working across geographical regions such as Europe, America and very recently, from South Asia and Eastern regions. These scholars have invented a whole new realm of academic inquiry with emerging themes and social patterns of impacts and

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usages. The present paper is designed to evaluate some of the emerging broader thematic patterns in mobile communication scholarship. However, this task could not be done without dealing with the basic questions such as what is the mobile phone? What is mobile communication? and what it does?

Mobile Phone, its Structure and Communicational Implications

Basically, mobile phone is a wireless, new media technology which provides networking communication across distance. It is a device which enables for mobile communication, therefore, regarded as a mobile communication technology. According to Campbell (2013) the mobile communication technologies are “devices and services that supported mediated social connectivity while the user is in physical motion” (p. 9). Due to its structural peculiarity of communicational mobility, many researches have been conducted to understand how it affects social communication and scholars came up with new processes. Terms like ‘connected presence’ (Licoppe, 2004), ‘perpetual contact’ (Katz and Aakhus, 2002) and ‘constant touch’ (Ager, 2003) capture the same phenomenon of relentless and permanent social connectivity which the mobile phone offers, which cannot be provided by earlier technologies. It is also said that the mobility aspect of the device has resulted in increased communicational reachability, direct addressability and interlacing of tasks (Ling and Donner, 2009). The widely cited concept of ‘microcoordination’ (Ling, 2004), which denotes nuanced mobile coordination among social actors, is also a product of the mobility aspect of the mobile phone. Secondly, the mobile communication technologies are often interactive, so the mobile phone. As a result, when compared to the earlier analogical mediums, social actors are more active as mobile users and communication process becomes more engaging, therefore less deterministic. Thirdly, it’s a digital medium, therefore, it works through a binary coding system. Its digital ability makes communication process far efficient as compared to the wireline

or other non-digital mediums. All the above mentioned characteristics such as mobility, interactivity and digital capacity make the mobile a new media device, which has somewhat different structure from that of early media system. There is no wonder that these structural peculiarities have given ways to far reaching social implications whom we will be dealing in the next section.

Emerging Themes of Social Impact

The academic curiosity to understand the social consequences of the mobile phone has paved the ways to form a new research field based on an interdisciplinary engagement as *Mobile Communication Studies*. The researchers from the field have come up with new emerging themes and concerns. For this purpose the scholars of the field not only engaged in the creative intellectual production exclusive to the field but also heavily borrowed methodological tools from the umbrella field called media and communication studies. Therefore, it stands out as not an unrelated field but has grown as a part of the broader field of media studies whose scope is far beyond the mobile communication. However, its empirical researches have set up new broad research themes.

One of the foremost research theme is associated with the question of mobile’s implication on social relationships or the sociability pattern. Three major studies by Ling (2004; 2008; 2012) clearly establish that the device is primarily used to maintain close and intimate ties of relationships such as those of friends and family. These researches also establish that although the mobile offer various social functions, however, for the users, it remains a taken-for-granted medium. Castells and his co-authors (2007) in their global, macro level overview also support the theme of sociability with close ties under the conceptual framework of networked sociability. In the Indian context, Tenhunen (2008; 2018) found that mobile phone use in rural India resulted in the strengthening of kinship ties and reinforcement of village sociability. Such themes of research are also supported by researchers working elsewhere where mobile

phone is correlated with micromanagement and reinforcement of social relationships.

Although the researches see mobile phone as a functional device with positive association with social life, however, on the contrary, it is also a technology which is associated with power and control. Empirical studies clearly reveal this correlation. In his research Yoon (2003) found that for the young people of South Korea, mobile has emerged as a controlling medium, where parents use the device to exercise remote control over them. Therefore, it goes contrary to the device's structure which is known to facilitate autonomy. Similarly, in an another study, Fotel and Thomsen (2002) also support the theme of parent's surveillance over children. These researches reveal that power dimension is a significant theme of mobile technology usages and shed light into how technology interacts with the power structure of the society.

An another domain of research interest deals with the question of mobile's impact on work-home balance. Some researches reveal that due to work-home blurring, the mobile has negatively affected family life and actually resulted in low degree of family satisfaction (Chesley, 2005). However, other rejected this pattern and maintain that such researches are actually exaggerations. In reality, the device is used for more mundane purposes such as maintaining social relationships (Wajcman et al., 2008). Therefore, so far, scholars have no agreement over blurring theme and more researches are needed to shed light upon it.

An another emerging and controversial theme is associated with the correlation between mobile phone and economic development. Jensen's (2007) research from Kerala clearly indicates the development pattern, where he found that the device allows fishermen to increase their income. Such studies of economic efficiency and monetary increase is also supported by other researches by economists. However, this pattern came under the critical scrutiny of Anthropological studies which reveal that mobile phone is not positively correlated with better income or jobs (Horst and Miller,

2006; Wallis, 2013). These areas of disagreements made the theme as highly debatable and unsettled. So far, therefore, we have mixed understanding regarding the theme of the impact of mobile communication on economic development.

There is no doubt that the mobile is increasingly used as a political tool by people across the world. This particular ability of mobile use for political processes let scholars to questions its implications of mobile on political participation, political activism and democratic processes. Rheingold (2002) saw mobile media as an efficient tool to organize protesting activities. He used the term '*smart mob*' to denote the instant mobilization of masses for political cause. Research work by Castells et al. (2007) referred to several examples from Philippines to South Korea where the phone appeared as a political tool for protestors, mobilizing around crucial political issues of their countries. Such types of findings are now very common in mobile communication literature and can be found across countries, including in India. Overall, it appears that the mobile media is clearly correlated with political processes. However, it has to be bore in mind that the phone itself does not responsible for political uses but it depends on the contextual factors of social actors, which included their motivations, orientations and desires which are articulated by the phone.

The above survey of researches shows that the mobile phone uses is releasing new social processes in different dimensions of social life. The field called mobile communication studies has emerged as a platform to observe, analyze and theorize these novel patterns. However, so far, the field is suffering from scarcity of published materials and much researches have come from developed regions of the West. However, very recently, as an effect of mobile's surge in Asia and other regions, new researches are emerging from these areas. However, despite of these contributions, there is a lot to add in the pool of knowledge and such an effort will definitely be helpful in

developing this new emerging field of intellectual inquiry.

Conclusion

There is no wonder that the mobile has become a ubiquitous social tool. Its implications for society and culture are multidimensional. It has consequences not only for the relational life but also for work, economy and politics as well. The field of mobile communication studies has contributed into the formation of new emerging themes and concerns. However, the field is still slowly moving with the problem of lack of published materials along with low interest in theoretical and conceptual formations. The western concentration of research is also a problem. For the proper development of the field, it requires cumulative works both from empirical as well as methodological sides, including efforts should come from cross cultural scholarship. However, our review suggests that the field is moving with some new and fresh insights into social processes and implications unleashed by the mobile phone. The paper concludes that the mobile communication studies has contributed in the knowledge production through its multidimensional researches and the process in ongoing with new scholars joining the field. However, more researches are needed to shed light into emerging research themes.

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